

2-Amino-1,4-disubstituted-3-cyanopyrroles (2): To the solution of (2-bromo-1-aryllalkylidene) propane-dinitrile (0.02 mol) in n-propanol (50 ml) was added primary aromatic amine (0.02 mol) dissolved in n-propanol (10 ml) portionwise with constant stirring at 60–5° over a period of 30 mins. After the completion of addition, reaction mixture was further stirred for 1 h at the same temperature and for 1 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was diluted with water (25 ml) and the solid separated was filtered, dried and crystallised (Table 1).

4-Amino-5,7-disubstituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyridines (3): A mixture of 2-amino-1,4-disubstituted-3-cyanopyrroles (2; 0.01 mol), formamide (15 ml), dimethylformamide (5 ml) and formic acid (2 ml) was refluxed for 6–8 h. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with cold ethanol, dried and crystallised (Table 1).

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Flavonoids of the Flowers of *Ichnocarpus frutescence*

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ICHNOCARPUS frutescence R. Br. (Apocynaceae), a medicinally important large evergreen laticiferous woody creeper with rusty red appearance and ascending upto an altitude of 4000 ft, is found throughout India¹⁻³. A literature survey revealed that no investigation of its flavonoid constituents has been carried out. In this communication, we

report the isolation of a flavonol and a flavonol glycoside from the methanolic extract of the fresh flowers of *I. frutescence* and their characterisation as quercetin and quercetin-3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside, respectively.

The concentrated methanolic extract of fresh flowers of the plant, collected locally, was fractionated successively with (i) petroleum ether, (ii) ether, (iii) ethyl acetate, (iv) butan-1-ol and (v) aqueous butan-1-ol (1 : 4). Shinoda test revealed that only ethyl acetate extract contained the flavonoid. This fraction was then chromatographed over a silica gel column and two flavonoids (compounds A and B) were obtained.

Compound A: It was eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 2) and crystallised from acetone-methanol (1 : 1) as yellow crystals, m.p. 316°; *R_f* 0.64 (BuOH-AcOH-H₂O, 6 : 1 : 2); gave positive Shinoda test but negative Molisch test. It was identified as quercetin on the basis of colour reactions, its penta-acetate (m.p. 197–98°), spectral analysis, co-pc and m.p.

Compound B: Further elution of the column using the same solvent gave compound B, crystallised as yellow needle shaped clustres, m.p. 235–36° (Found: C, 54.39; H, 4.29. C₂₁H₂₀O₁₂ requires: C, 54.31; H, 4.31%); *M⁺* 464; *R_f* 0.58 (BuOH-AcOH-H₂O); gave olive-green colouration with FeCl₃; gave orange-red Shinoda test and positive Molisch test; the dull brown coloration with uv, changed to bright yellow when exposed to uv/NH₃; λ_{max} 254, 370 (MeOH), 269, 417 (+NaOMe), 276, 388 (+NaOAc), 260, 385 (+NaOAc/H₂BO₃), 272, 438 (+AlCl₃), 268, 405 nm (+AlCl₃/HCl). λ_{max} 254 and 370 nm indicated the compound B to be a flavonol glycoside. On acid hydrolysis it gave an aglycone, m.p. 315.5°, identified as quercetin. The sugar was identified as D-glucose by co-tlc⁴. The aglycone-sugar ratio⁵ was found to be 1 : 1, suggesting compound B to be a monoglucoside of quercetin. A bathochromic shift of 68 nm in band-I absorption with AlCl₃ indicated the sugar linkage at 3-position⁶. Periodate oxidation and formic acid estimation suggested the pyranose form of D-glucose⁷. The pmr spectra of the glucoside acetate, in addition to typical signals for quercetin skeleton exhibited seven glucosyl protons (δ-ppm 5.61–3.82). Hydrolysability of the glucoside with almond emulsin showed β-linkage⁸. Thus compound B was characterised as quercetin-3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside.

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